

**New use of Li/MnO₂ batteries under renewable overvoltage as thermal power generators:
energy and exergy analysis**

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Abstract

Lithium-ion batteries are widely used to store electrical energy for applications such as solar power, consumer electronics or automotive. However, once their electrical energy storage capacity is exhausted, they constitute hazardous waste that also has a high environmental impact and whose recycling process consumes large amounts of energy. In this study, a thermodynamic and heat transfer study was conducted on lithium-ion batteries subjected to electrical overvoltage to quantify the thermal energy generated. Thus, a detailed mathematical model of a renewable electric power surge process applied to a lithium manganese oxide cathode battery was developed for use as a renewable thermal energy source. Furthermore, the model was evaluated using experimental data under various overvoltage and battery charging conditions. As a result, energy and exergy analysis was used to determine the configuration that provides the highest energy and exergy efficiency or performance for both new and used batteries. Thus, the maximum energy efficiency value was 81% for new batteries and 4% for used batteries, whereas the exergy efficiency reached a maximum value of 5% for new batteries and 1.6% for used batteries. These results allow lithium-ion batteries to be considered as thermal energy sources, opening the possibility of new uses, valorising the waste generated at the end of the current useful life of these devices, and reducing their carbon footprint.

Keywords

Energy and exergetic analysis; lithium-ion batteries; MnO_2 cathode; energy storage; resource saving; SDG 12.

Highlights

- Energy and exergetic analysis with experimental validation of a lithium-ion battery subjected to overvoltage.
- Calculation of energy and exergy efficiency as well as the maximum available work of a lithium-ion battery used as a thermal energy source.
- Thermal power generation in a lithium-ion battery using electrical energy from a renewable source.
- Reuse of spent lithium-ion batteries as sources of thermal energy.

Abbreviations

BTMS: Battery thermal management system.

COP: Coefficient of performance.

EVs: Electric vehicles.

HEVs: Hybrid electric vehicles.

PCM: Phase change materials.

SDG: Sustainable development goal.

1. Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries have become an essential element of life today, storing energy and providing portable and rechargeable power to electronic devices as well as pure electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs). The configuration of lithium-ion batteries is typical of more classical electrochemical batteries [1]. They are made up of a container, two electrodes (anode and cathode), a liquid or solid electrolyte material, and a permeable membrane that allows ionic movement between the electrodes and prevents short circuits between them. They constitute the basic components of a cell. Thus, current is produced by the oxidation and reduction reactions between the electrolyte and the electrodes of the cell. The electrolyte next to the electrode releases electrons (it is oxidised) when the battery is connected to a load. While this occurs, the process is completed when the ions next to the other electrode accept the electrons (it is reduced). On the other hand, this procedure is reversed when the batteries are charged. There are several lithium-ion batteries on the market that vary in the material used for their cathode, with iron phosphate, cobalt oxide, and manganese oxide being the most common materials [2]. Iron phosphate batteries have lower energy densities than those using other cathode materials. This results in lower voltages, making them unsuitable for certain applications such as high-performance automotive [3]. Cobalt oxide cathodes have several drawbacks, including toxicity and high cost due to the scarcity of cobalt [4]. However, manganese oxide cathode batteries are very interesting due to their non-toxic, safe, low cost due to the abundance of manganese, good high-rate capability as well as low-rate capability, high performance, and excellent shelf life [5], [6]. Thus, one of the most popular cathode materials in primary Li-ion batteries is MnO_2 , and its usage in secondary Li-ion batteries has also been researched [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. Therefore, the analysis performed in this study will focus on a primary Li/ MnO_2 battery. Figure 1 shows the operating diagram of a Li/ MnO_2 battery, where the direction of circulation of electrons (direction of the electric current) and lithium ions is represented in the charging and discharging process of the battery.

Fig. 1. Scheme of Li/ MnO_2 battery operation

During battery discharge, which is the process that allows the battery to supply power to an external device, electrons flow from the anode to the cathode through an external circuit, thus generating electrical current. Lithium ions also flow from anode to cathode through the electrolyte. During the charging process, the direction of the cycle is reversed. That is, the circulation of electrons and Li^+ ions occurs from the cathode to the anode, and the chemical reactions also occur in the opposite direction. During the charging process, the lithium ions migrate to the negative electrode, where they react with the electrons to intercalate in the solid particles of manganese oxide, forming LiMn_2O_4 molecules. Furthermore, during this process, each LiC_6 molecule on the anode breaks down into pure carbon, a Li^+ ion, and an electron (e^-). Thus, the reactions that take place inside a Li/ MnO_2 cell or battery are as follows [12]:

Reaction at the positive electrode (cathode)

Reaction at the negative electrode (anode)

Considering the sense of the reactions during the charge and discharge of the battery the following:

Despite all the advantages that lithium batteries have, at the end of their useful life, they become a waste that generates a large amount of energy and economic investment to recover part of its components [13], [14]. To assess this potential waste and reduce the carbon footprint of these batteries, this research was conducted to study the thermal behaviour of lithium batteries and to describe the mathematical and physicochemical models for the use of the thermal energy generated in these devices. With the increasing use of renewable energies and other technologies that use storage batteries [15], [16], [17], it is necessary to develop new efficient technological processes that reduce their environmental impact. Likewise, achieving sustainable development based on the use of renewable energy and the development of energy efficiency is a necessity within the economic model of the European Union (EU) [18], [19]. This growing global concern about climate change caused by greenhouse gases (GHG) has recently translated into increasing regulations regarding polluting emissions and waste generation [20], [21]. Thus, the new European Regulation [22] aims to promote a circular economy by regulating cells and batteries throughout their entire life cycle. In this context, this research showed that lithium batteries could be used to store energy in the form of heat, to be used later or directly, by converting electrical energy into thermal energy.

The generation of thermal energy in these devices is based on the principle of conversion of the chemical energy released in the chemical reactions caused in the battery when it is subjected to an electric current. To achieve this goal, the batteries were subjected to power overvoltage that activated the chemical processes of oxidation and reduction and generated heating of the material from which the battery was made up by the Joule effect. Therefore, diagnosing the amount of thermal energy available in these batteries, to be used later and generate work, and quantifying the maximum useful work available, was of great interest. This interest was increased by using a photovoltaic solar energy installation as a source of electrical energy. Energy of a totally renewable nature and without associated polluting emissions. As a result, with the combination of electrical energy from a renewable source and lithium batteries, it was possible to generate clean thermal energy. This process was especially interesting when the batteries used ended their useful life as electrical energy stores, going from being a waste product to an energetically and economically recoverable product. Figure 2 represents the process of harnessing electrical energy from a renewable source to obtain thermal energy and useful work through lithium batteries.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the thermal energy generation process in lithium batteries and its use to generate useful work

According to the analysis of the thermal energy generated by lithium batteries, various studies have been conducted, but all of them minimize the impact of this energy on the operation of the battery as an electrical energy store. Thus, in 2020, Lamrani et al. presented a thermal model of lithium battery simulating phase transition processes in battery materials using a heat source [23]. Following a similar line of research, in 2022 Wang et al. developed another numerical model based on the comparison of phase change materials for thermal management of hybrid batteries [24]. Using nanomaterials, Anqi et al. [25] and de Bais et al. developed a battery thermal management system (BTMS) [26]. In 2015, Ling et al. studied heat buildup in lithium batteries by analysing a combined system of phase change materials (PCM) and forced air convection [27]. In this last case, the investigation was not interested in the use of this thermal energy generated in the batteries, but rather tried to find a solution to the overheating of batteries. In 2018, Hussain et al. analysed the thermal management of these batteries using different materials to avoid heating during use [28]. In addition, the thermal energy generated was studied in 2016 and 2022 to extend the life of lithium batteries in EVs and HEVs [29], [30].

The study performed in this article focused on lithium batteries with a manganese oxide cathode, which is currently one of the most widely used cathodes. However, it allows us to define the process of calculating the thermodynamic characteristics of any other type of lithium battery cathode chemistry. Thus, a mathematical model was created to quantify the amount of thermal energy that can be obtained from a lithium battery subjected to overvoltage. In addition, a mathematical model was developed to calculate the amount of entropy, the destroyed exergy or irreversibility, and the maximum or reversible work that can be obtained during the process. The uses of these thermal energy generators into which lithium batteries are converted were not analysed in this research but are expected to be very diverse. Among others, lithium batteries could be used as heat sources or to use the generated thermal energy for mechanical work.

The novelties and main contributions of this work are as follows:

1. For the first time, a thermodynamic and heat transfer study was conducted on lithium-ion batteries subjected to power overvoltage to quantify the thermal energy generated.
2. A detailed mathematical model of an overvoltage process using renewable electrical energy in a lithium manganese oxide cathode battery as a thermal energy source was developed. In addition, the model was evaluated using experimental data under various conditions of temperature, battery combinations, thermal insulation, and overvoltage.

3. Exergy and energy analysis was used to determine the configuration that provided the highest energy and exergy efficiency or performance in both new and used batteries. For this purpose, different electrical and thermal configurations of the battery groups were analysed.

4. An effective energy and exergetic calculation method was provided for the consideration of lithium-ion batteries as sources of thermal energy to increase the energy efficiency of these energy storage devices and reduce the polluting emissions generated by the used batteries.

2. Dynamic model and experimental installation

2.1. Description of model and experimental installation

The battery model used in the tests was a lithium battery with a manganese oxide cathode, a charge capacity of 800 mAh and a voltage of 3 V. To supply electrical overvoltage to the battery, its poles or terminals were connected to a power source. Electrical energy was obtained from a photovoltaic solar installation located on the roof of the laboratory. Subsequently, this energy from a renewable source was used to supply, through an electrical power source, different overvoltage to the lithium battery. For the measurements, thermocouple K-type temperature measuring devices with protective metal sheath (0° to +1100°C / -180° to -1300°C) were connected to the battery surface, data were recorded using a Cometsystem datalogger model MS6D and downloaded via the Monitoring Systems MS series software. In this way, the surface temperatures of the battery under overvoltage for 290 minutes were obtained. Ambient temperatures and atmospheric pressures were also recorded in the different tests. Figure 3 shows the experimental facility. The mathematical model obtained for a single battery was applied to different tests with different battery arrangements as follows.

Fig. 3 Experimental facility

2.2. Model validation

When the battery was subjected to an electric current, its surface heated steadily over time until it reached a maximum value. Simultaneously, heat transfer from the battery to the surroundings was generated. This consideration was used to validate the proposed model by calculating the heat released by the battery during this period of temperature loss. The heat was calculated in two ways, and the results were compared. The first way is through an energy balance of the overvoltage process in the battery. The second method involves applying a formula that relates the amount of heat exchanged by a substance of a given mass and specific heat and generates a given temperature variation. The energy model is detailed in point 4, and the formula relating the heat given off to the specific heat of the substance, which is a known and validated equation in classical thermodynamics, is as follows:

$$Q = m \cdot c \cdot \Delta T \quad (3)$$

Where:

Q is the heat exchanged in J.

m is the mass of the substance in kg.

c is the specific heat of the substance in $\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$.

ΔT is the temperature variation experienced in the substance in K or °C.

2.3. Dynamic tests description

2.3.1. Test 1 by applying a voltage of 5 V to a charged battery

A single charged lithium battery (3.28 V) was tested at a constant voltage of 5 V for 100 min. Under these conditions, and keeping the ambient temperature constant at 20 °C, the outside temperature of the battery was measured. The maximum temperature was obtained at 9.1 min and was 82.20 °C. This temperature was reached rapidly by heat transfer from the interior of the battery to the surface. Once this maximum peak was reached, there was a rapid decrease in the surface temperature. This was due to the temperature loss caused by a constant flow of heat to the environment and the end of the chemical reactions that occurred during the loading process, as reflected in point 1. With a small temperature rise reached shortly after 20 min of testing, the temperature starts to slowly decrease to a constant value between 50 and 60 degrees Celsius. On the other hand, two gas leaks occurred at the cathode. The first leak occurred after less than 1 minute and the second one after 9 minutes of testing.

2.3.2. Test 2 by applying a voltage of 10 V to a charged battery

Once test 1 was completed, and without interruption in the supply of electrical current to the battery, a constant voltage of 10 V was applied for 190 min. As in the previous case, the ambient temperature was maintained at 20 °C, and the outside temperature of the battery was measured. The maximum temperature was obtained at 2.03 min and was 85.21 °C. As in test 1, heat transfer from the inside of the battery to the surface rapidly reached this temperature. The temperature drops after reaching this maximum peak were also rapid, and on this occasion, there was no temperature recovery during this process of temperature decrease. During the process of temperature increase, the current intensity also increased, reaching a maximum peak of 1.29 A at 0.92 min after starting with a 10 V overvoltage. Figures 4 and 5 represent the data obtained from tests 1 and 2. The blue curve indicates the variations in the intensity of the electrical current as a function of time, and the orange curve shows the variation in the temperature on the surface of the battery as a function of time.

Fig. 4. Effect of a 5 V overvoltage applied to a Li/MnO₂ charged battery for 100 minutes. Diagram Temperature vs. Time

Fig. 5. Effect of a 10 V overvoltage applied to a Li/MnO₂ charged battery for 190 minutes. Diagram Temperature vs. Time

2.3.3. Test 3 by applying a voltage of 5 V to a discharged battery

The same lithium battery used in the previous tests was tested at a constant voltage of 5 V for 144 minutes. In this test, the battery was discharged at a polymer voltage of 1.85 V. Under these conditions and keeping the ambient temperature constant at 20 °C, the outside temperature of the battery was measured. During the test, practically no current flowed through the battery. The surface temperature of the battery barely increased by 2 °C and subsequently stabilized, and the current dropped to 0 A, as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Effect of a 5 V overvoltage applied to a Li/MnO₂ discharged battery for 144 minutes. Diagram Temperature vs. Time

2.3.4. Test 4 by applying a voltage of 10 V to a discharged battery

At minute 144 of test 3, the source voltage was increased to 10 V. No current continued to flow through the battery despite the source voltage being increased. However, at minute 151, a current of 0.01 A started to flow and the battery temperature slowly increased to a maximum of 47.72 °C. It is shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Effect of a 10 V overvoltage applied to a Li/MnO₂ discharged battery for 460 minutes. Diagram Temperature vs. Time

3. Energy analysis

3.1. Energy balance

The energy balance based on the first law of thermodynamics applied to the dynamic model is detailed below. For this, the development by Çenge et al. for chemically reactive closed systems at rest was used [31], according to the following equation:

$$(Q_{in} - Q_{out}) + (W_{in} - W_{out}) = U_{products} - U_{reagents} \quad (4)$$

Where $U_{products}$ is the internal energy of the products and $U_{reagents}$ is the internal energy of the reagents.

Using the definition of enthalpy, which states that:

$$\bar{u} = \bar{h} - P \cdot \bar{v} \quad (5)$$

Or

$$\bar{u}_f^0 + \bar{u} - \bar{u}^0 = \bar{h}_f^0 + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 - P \cdot \bar{v} \quad (6)$$

The energy balance can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{in} + W_{in} + \sum_{reagents} N_r \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 - P \cdot \bar{v}) = \\ = Q_{out} + W_{out} + \sum_{products} N_p \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 - P \cdot \bar{v}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Verifying that the energy supplied to the system by the battery under overvoltage is equal to the energy leaving the system. This incoming energy consisted of surge electrical work and outgoing energy in the form of heat given off by the battery. The energy balance resulting from the endothermic and exothermic reactions generated during the battery charging process was added to these two energies. The system analysed was the dynamic model defined in section 2.1.

Where:

Q_{in} is the heat-entering the system.

Q_{out} is the heat-leaving the system.

W_{in} is the work done on the system.

W_{out} is the work the system does on the environment.

N_r is the number of reagents moles per mole of total reacting material.

N_p is the number of product moles per mole of total reacting material.

\bar{h}_f^0 is the enthalpy of formation in the reference state, i.e., at 25 °C and 1 atm.

\bar{h} is the reagent or product enthalpy under the conditions which the reaction occurs.

\bar{h}^0 is the reagent or product enthalpy in the reference state, i.e., at 25 °C and 1 atm.

P is the reagent or product pressure.

\bar{v} is the reagent or product specific volume.

The $P \cdot \bar{v}$ terms are negligible when dealing with liquids or solids. Thus, this value was not considered. The environmental conditions were $T_0 = 25$ °C and $P_0 = 1$ atm of atmospheric pressure. Therefore, under these conditions $\bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 = c_p \cdot (T - 25$ °C), where c_p is the heat capacity

at constant pressure of the reactant or product. Table 1 reflects the values of the different heat capacities as reflected by Perry et al. in his renowned chemical engineer's handbook [32] and the investigations carried out by Bagci et al. [33], Delhaes et al. [34] and Yamaura et al. [35]. The value of the enthalpy of formation in the reference state for the reactants and products has been obtained from Perry et al. [32], Nakajima et al. [36] and Wang & Navrotsky [37]. The mass of the different reactants and products of the reactions that occurs at the anode and cathode of the battery are also listed in this table.

Table 1. Values of heat capacities, enthalpies of formation and mass for the different compounds present at the electrodes of the lithium battery with manganese oxide cathode

	$c_p \left(\frac{J}{mol \cdot K} \right)$	$\bar{h}_f^0 \left(\frac{kJ}{mol} \right)$	mass (g)
C	$11.19 + 0.01096 \cdot T - \frac{489436.9}{T^2}$	0	4
LiMn ₂ O ₄	$0.002 \cdot T^2 + 0.28 \cdot T$	-1368.1 ± 1.8	3.6
LiC ₆	$(0.003 \pm 0.00015) \cdot T + (0.000065 \pm 0.000006) \cdot T^3$	-241.7	5.28
Mn ₂ O ₄	$80.60 + 0.22525 \cdot T - 0.0000875 \cdot T^2$	1041.8	4.8

The energy balance identifies both the input and output work (W) done on or by the system consisting of the overvoltage batteries, as well as the heat (Q) administered or produced by the system and the net transfer of energy into the system (represented by the sum of reagents), or out of the system per mole of reacting material (represented by the sum of products). The system was subjected to an electrical overvoltage which defined a $W_{in} = I \cdot V$, where I is the current intensity and V is the value of the electrical current.

With the characteristics described above, the test presented an energy balance was simplified to:

$$W_{in} + \sum_{reagents} N_r \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C)) = Q_{out} + \sum_{products} N_p \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C)) \quad (8)$$

Or

$$\dot{W}_{in} + \sum_{reagents} \dot{n}_r \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C)) = \dot{Q}_{out} + \sum_{products} \dot{n}_p \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C)) \quad (9)$$

Where \dot{n}_p and \dot{n}_r represent the molar flow rate of product p and reactant r, respectively.

3.2. Calculation of internal temperature knowing the battery surface temperature

Ignoring the effect of heat transfer by internal convection, since the internal convection film coefficient is unknown, and its impact is insignificant; the overall heat transfer coefficient is calculated as follows:

$$U = \frac{1}{r_2 \cdot \frac{\ln \left(\frac{r_2}{r_1} \right)}{k}} = \frac{k}{r_2 \cdot \ln \left(\frac{r_2}{r_1} \right)} \quad (10)$$

Where r_1 is the inner radius of the cylindrical lithium battery, r_2 is the outer radius, including the outer paint and the thickness of the metal cylinder and k the thermal conductivity coefficient of the battery metallic material. Table 2 represents the dimensions and properties of the analysed battery. Being c the specific heat of the battery.

Table 2. Dimensions and properties of the Li/MnO₂ battery

r_1	(m)	0.00689
r_2	(m)	0.00760
L	(m)	0.02450
k	$\left(\frac{W}{m \cdot K}\right)$	54 [38]
c	$\left(\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}\right)$	1040 [39]-[42]

Therefore,

$$\dot{Q}_{out} = U \cdot S \cdot \Delta T \quad (11)$$

Where, S represents the outer surface area of the battery and its value was calculated as $S = 2\pi \cdot r_2 \cdot L$, where L is the length of the battery. Furthermore, $\Delta T = T_s - T_i$. Where T_s is the temperature measured on the surface of the battery and T_i is the temperature inside the battery.

3.3. Energy efficiency

The value of the energy efficiency of the process was calculated by applying the first law of thermodynamics according to the following equation:

$$\eta_{energetic} = COP = \frac{Q}{W} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{out}}{\dot{W}_{in}} \quad (12)$$

4. Entropy and exergy analysis

4.1. Entropy balance

Continuing with the thermodynamic analysis of the battery overvoltage process, the entropy change of the system was analysed through an entropy balance that allowed obtaining the entropy generated in the process. Subsequently, the destroyed exergy was obtained. In both cases, the equations were based on the theoretical developments of the well-known texts of Çengel et al. and Bejar et al. [31], [43]:

$$S_{in} - S_{out} + S_{generated} = \Delta S_{sistema} = S_{products} - S_{reagents} \quad (13)$$

where $S_{generated}$ is the entropy generated by the system, $S_{products}$ and $S_{reagents}$ are the entropy of products and reactants of the chemical reactions respectively. Furthermore, in our case the incoming entropy (S_{in}), the outgoing entropy (S_{out}) and the difference between the entropy of products ($S_{products}$) and reagents ($S_{reagents}$) was calculated as follows:

$$S_{in} = \frac{Q_{in}}{T_{border}} = \frac{Q_{in}}{T_s} = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$S_{out} = \frac{Q_{out}}{T_{border}} = \frac{Q_{out}}{T_s} \quad (15)$$

$$S_{products} - S_{reagents} = \sum_{products} N_p \cdot \bar{S}_p(T, P) - \sum_{reagents} N_r \cdot \bar{S}_r(T, P) \quad (16)$$

Being:

$$\bar{S}_i(T, P_i) = \bar{S}_i^0(T, P_0) - R \cdot \ln \frac{y_i \cdot P_m}{P_0} \quad (17)$$

Where:

$\overline{S}_i^0(T, P_0)$ is the formation entropy (at T and $P_0 = 1$ atm).

R is the universal ideal gas constant = $0.08206 \frac{\text{atm}\cdot\text{L}}{\text{mol}\cdot\text{K}} = 8.314 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol}\cdot\text{K}}$.

N_r is the number of reagent moles.

N_p is the number of product moles.

P_i is the partial pressure.

$P_0 = 1$ atm.

P_m is the total pressure of reactants or products mixture, calculated as:

$$P_m = \frac{m \cdot R}{V} \cdot T \quad (18)$$

y_i is the mole fraction of each component i (it can be a reactant or a product). This value is equal to 1 for independent solids. Being V and m the total volume and number of moles of reagents or products respectively and depending on whether the entropy of reagents or products is calculated. The value of V for the cylindrical battery was $\pi \cdot r_{in}^2 \cdot L$, as measured in Table 2. The entropy of formation value in the reference state for the reactants and products were obtained from Perry et al. [32] and are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Entropy of formation values for the different compounds present at the electrodes of the lithium battery with manganese oxide cathode

	$\overline{S}_i^0(T, P_0)$ ($\frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{mol}\cdot\text{K}}$)
Mn ₂ O ₄	-106.20
C ₆ (graphite)	5.74
LiC ₆	-47.84
LiMn ₂ O ₄	92.80

4.2. Destroyed exergy

The calculation of the destroyed exergy or irreversibility of the overcharging process in the lithium battery was calculated by the equation:

$$X_{destroyed} = T_0 \cdot S_{generated} \quad (19)$$

Recalling that T_0 represented the ambient or surrounding temperature and was 298 K, then:

$$X_{destroyed} = 298 \text{ K} \cdot S_{generated} \quad (20)$$

4.3. Exergy efficiency

The value of the exergy efficiency of the process was calculated by applying the second law of thermodynamics according to the following equation:

$$\eta_{energetic} = COP_{rev} = \frac{T_H}{T_H - T_C} \quad (21)$$

Where T_H is the temperature inside the battery and T_C the temperature on the outer surface of the battery.

5. Maximum or reversible work

In the case analysed, where there was only heat transfer to the surroundings and in the absence of change in kinetic and potential energies, the reversible or maximum work (W_{max}) that could theoretically be done during the process, was calculated according to the following formula based on the literature of Çengel et al. and Bejar et al. [31], [43]:

$$W_{max} = \sum_{reagents} N_r \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 - T_0 \cdot \bar{s}) - \sum_{products} N_p \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^0 - T_0 \cdot \bar{s}) \quad (22)$$

Therefore, as defined above:

$$W_{max} = \sum_{reagents} N_r \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C) - T_0 \cdot \bar{s})_r - \sum_{products} N_p \cdot (\bar{h}_f^0 + c_p \cdot (T - 25^\circ C) - T_0 \cdot \bar{s})_p \quad (23)$$

6. Results

6.1. Test 1 applying a voltage of 5 V to a charged battery

The results of the model validation reflected the reliability of the energy model used. Thus, similar values were obtained using equations (3) and (8) to obtain the heat released by the battery from the beginning of test 1 until the maximum battery surface temperature was reached. These values are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Value of the maximum heat given off by the battery under a voltage of 5 V

Equation used	Q (J)	Battery surface temperature range (°C)
(3)	1 487.82	25-82.2
(8)	1 434.48	25-82.2

The value of Q differs by 3.6 %, and this variation could be due to small changes in the weight of the battery, in the values of the thermal constants used or in the precision of the electrical measurement devices. Therefore, the value of the thermal energy released in the form of heat and calculated with the energy balance, is fully assumable and allows obtaining the following values of entropy generated, exergy destroyed, and maximal or reversible work, as shown in Figure 8.

6.2. Test 2 applying a voltage of 10 V to a charged battery

Table 5 details the Q values obtained from the end of test 1 to the maximum heat released by applying a 10 V surge. In addition, Figure 8 reflects the value of the maximum entropy generated, exergy destroyed, and the maximal or reversible work of the battery under a voltage of 10 V.

Table 5. Values of the maximum heat given off by the battery under a voltage of 10 V

Equation used	Q (J)	Battery surface temperature range (°C)
(3)	841.18	50-85.2
(8)	841.22	50-85.2

The Q value obtained using different methods is similar, which confirms the validity of the energy balance method.

Fig. 8. Values of the maximum entropy generated, exergy destroyed, maximal or reversible work, and maximum energetic and exergetic efficiency of the charged battery under voltages of 5 V and 10 V

The increase in electrical voltage to which the charged battery was subjected was 100% (from 5 V to 10 V) and produced the results shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Q , $S_{generated}$, $X_{destroyed}$ and W_{max} increments by varying the power applied to the charged battery from 5 V to 10 V

6.3. Test 3 applying a voltage of 5 V to a discharged battery

No significant temperature rise in the battery was achieved with this test and therefore no thermal energy in the form of heat, entropy, work, or exergy variation has been generated.

6.4. Test 4 applying a voltage of 10 V to a discharged battery

A maximum increase of 27.72 °C in the surface temperature of the battery was observed. The reactions that occurred were not known, but they had a marked endothermic character since the heat value obtained with equation 3 and which was $Q = 663.06$ J was lower than the thermal energy provided to the battery during the overvoltage process due to the Joule effect. The maximum values for energy and exergy performance were 3.93% and 1.60%, respectively.

8. Conclusion

The feasibility of a method for calculating the thermal energy, entropy generated, exergy destroyed, and maximum work generated by a Li/MnO₂ battery when subjected to an electric current was demonstrated and experimentally validated. Two different configurations were analysed (new or charged battery and discharged battery) under two overvoltage conditions (5 V and 10 V) generated on the battery using electrical energy from a renewable source. The calculation method could be applied to different types of batteries with different cathode materials, provided that the thermal characteristics of the different chemical reactions taking place in the overvoltage processes were considered.

Furthermore, it was found that doubling the electrical voltage applied to the battery (from 5 V to 10 V) increased the maximum work generated by 110.4%, the exergy destroyed by 109.7%, the entropy generated by 99.5% and the thermal energy generated by 56.5%. Therefore, this voltage increase can be considered useful in the case of trying to achieve the maximum work that the battery can provide or in the case of needing higher thermal energies than those achieved with lower current voltages. However, the heat gain generated was reduced to just over 50% compared to that achieved with 5 V and was therefore not as interesting.

On the other hand, after a short period of time and once the maximum temperatures had been reached, the temperature on the outside of the new battery subjected to an external electric current was approximately 50-60 °C for both 5 V and 10 V. In the case of the used battery, the temperature increase was negligible at 5 V overvoltage and reached values below 50 °C at 10 V. The energy and exergetic efficiency of the process in the new battery were lower at 10 V than at 5 V. Both values decreased significantly in the case of the discharged battery. This situation makes it uninteresting to subject the battery to higher voltages. However, in the discharged battery, the 10 V voltage was necessary to generate thermal energy increases with temperature rises up to 28 °C, while 5 V was not sufficient. Thus, the maximum energy efficiency value was 81% for new batteries and 4% for used batteries, whereas the exergy efficiency reached a maximum value of 5% for new batteries and 1.6% for used batteries.

These results would meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development adopted by the United Nations. SDG 12 targets sustainable production and consumption. This goal can be achieved by reducing waste generation through recycling and reuse. Thus, the feasibility of recycling and reuse of used or new lithium batteries was demonstrated through the thermal recovery discussed in this article. Consequently, and according to the 2030 Agenda, the pollutant emissions associated with lithium batteries would be reduced.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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